

1 **BTLA and CTLA4 are silenced in the blood of humans with high CRP.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 The acute phase protein CRP is used as a marker of cardiovascular disease risk. We measured total
8 transcription in the blood of humans with low or no CRP and in humans with very high CRP to identify
9 causative factors that might account for elevated CVD risk associated with high CRP in humans. We
10 identified activation of exhaustion receptors BTLA and CTLA4 in the hematopoietic compartment in
11 humans with high CRP. In cardiovascular tissues and in cells of the heart, the number one most closely
12 regulated gene across the human transcriptome by BTLA and CTLA4 was the myocardial
13 infarction-related non-coding RNA transcript *MIAT*. BTLA could directly modulate expression of MIAT in
14 human cells and MIAT ncRNA expression correlated with PD-L1 expression *in vivo*. We recently described
15 cardinal differences in expression of BTLA and CTLA4 in human cancer, and defined these exhaustion
16 pathway components as intrinsically linked with the senescence program. The senescence pathway and
17 exhaustion program are likely important components of and contributors to cardiovascular disease risk in
18 humans.
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